

High-Yield Production of SiV-Doped Nanodiamonds for Spectroscopy and Sensing Applications

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graphical abstract

- unique bottom-up and top-down approach for fabrication of nanoporous diamond films
- surface sensitive SiV PL to H-/O-terminations due to their near-surface location
- nanodiamonds with bright and stable PL at 738 nm
- PL sensitivity to temperature
- universal technological methodology adaptable to produce differently doped NDs

Abstract

Nanodiamonds (NDs) containing optically active centers have gained significant relevance as the material of choice for biological, optoelectronic, and quantum applications. However, current production methods lag behind real needs. This study introduces two novel CVD-based approaches for fabricating NDs with optically active silicon-vacancy (SiV) color centers: the Bottom-Up (BU) and the Top-Down (TD) methods. The BU approach generates nanoporous diamond films with a core-shell structure, while the TD method employs molten-salt thermal etching to create uniform porous structures from ultrananocrystalline diamond films. Comprehensive characterization using advanced techniques revealed distinct morphologies and optical properties for each approach. The BU method yielded higher-

quality diamond phases with top-surface incorporation of SiV centers, while the TD method demonstrated efficient non-diamond phase removal.

Ultrasonic disintegration of both porous films produced NDs ranging from 40-500 nm, with unique morphologies characteristic of each approach. Photoluminescence measurements confirmed SiV centers (738 nm) in all NDs, exhibiting sensitivity to surface terminations, particularly in BU samples. Temperature-resolved spectroscopy shows the potential of the fabricated NDs for nano thermometry over a wide range of temperatures up to 100 °C. The zero-phonon line shows 0.022 ± 0.003 nm/K sensitivity, while the linewidth exhibits 0.068 ± 0.004 nm/K broadening.

The presented BU and TD methods offer significant advantages over existing techniques, including streamlined production processes, high-yield ND synthesis with tailored properties, and the potential for scalable, cost-effective manufacturing.

Introduction

Diamond is recognized as a perspective multi-functional material for various multidisciplinary uses. Today, the synthesis of diamond films by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) process has become a routine in laboratories and companies worldwide [1]. Doping of diamond with foreign atoms (nitrogen, silicon, germanium, tin, etc.) can result in the formation of photoluminescent optical centers making them preferable for photonic applications, quantum technologies, optically active markers for life science and sensors, etc. [2–6]. From the large family of photoluminescent optical centers (>400), silicon-vacancy (SiV) has received lot of attention due to stable and non-blinking photoluminescence (PL) with a sharp emission band at the near-infrared spectral region with the zero-phonon line at 738 nm. SiV naturally appears in the diamond films as a result of the self-doping process when the Si substrates are used or when the CVD growth is performed with the presence of Si, SiC, or quartz solid sources [7–9]. Fully controllable doping profiles with Si atoms can be realized by adding Si-containing gases (e.g. silane, tetramethylsilane) to the CVD growth mixture [10–12]. Finally, ion implantation can also be used to incorporate Si into the diamond crystal structure with excellent spatial control [13].

Instead of the SiV diamond films, the diamond nano-sized form known as nanodiamonds (NDs) is additionally advantageous [14] and highly demanded in bio-imaging and labeling [12,15]. So far, only a few techniques have proven the ability to produce NDs with SiV centers such as high-pressure high-temperature (HPHT) synthesis [16–18] and even detonation synthesis [19]. The CVD technology, in principle, offers great control over diamond doping in terms of the precursor quality and its concentration as well as over the morphology and phase composition of the diamond film. However, the apparent limitation of CVD technology for the preparation of NDs is the compactness of conventional CVD layers and very energetic methods must be used to produce NDs [20]. Several strategies can overcome this limitation. For example, by tuning the growth conditions of the CVD process towards the high power densities, 100-400 nm loose diamond particles with NV, SiV, and GeV centers were obtained [21,22]. The compactness of CVD layers can also be overcome by introducing the pores that would make the disintegration easier by using more gentle methods such as sonication. It has been recently shown that by using a special growth mode a porous morphology of the nanocrystalline diamond (NCD) layer can be achieved by bottom-up [23–25] or top-down approaches [26–28]. Here, the porous morphology can be envisioned as a highly suitable material platform for NDs preparation thanks to its brittleness and easy breakability into individual crystalline nano-grains. Such obtained NDs would utilize the excellent control of the CVD technique over the diamond properties including controlled doping. Finally, one can envision a layer that has a high content of the sp^2 -C grain boundary phase which effectively separates the individual diamond nanocrystals. This is a common visualization of so-called ultra nanocrystalline diamond (UNCD) layers. By using a proper treatment [29,30], the interparticle non-diamond phase could be selectively etched away and then the individual NDs could be obtained.

In this work, we establish the direct bottom-up growth and the unique top-down treatment of diamond thin films to achieve highly porous diamond structures which are used as the basis for the fabrication of NDs with SiV optical centers (SiV NDs). In particular, we developed the two proposed viable approaches for SiV ND preparation and compare them from the perspective of SiV optical properties, ND structure, size, and yield. Temperature-resolved spectroscopy is used to demonstrate that

NDs can potentially be used for nano thermometry over a wide range of temperatures, exhibiting a linear red shift in the zero-phonon-line and spectral broadening with increasing temperature.

Experimental

Material fabrication and processing

One-sided polished silicon (100) substrates of size 1x1 cm² were used for CVD diamond growth. First, the Si substrates were cleaned in an ultrasonic bath (Transonic T490 DH, Elma, f=40 kHz) in isopropanol followed by rinsing with deionized (DI) water and then seeded in a detonation nanodiamonds water-based suspension in the same ultrasonic bath according to [31]. Porous diamond films were fabricated by either a bottom-up (BU) or top-down (TD) approach.

BU approach

Firstly, diamond films (thickness <500 nm) with porous morphology were grown in the linear antenna pulsed microwave (MW) plasma system (AK 400, Roth & Rau) [32]. The microwave power was supplied through two linear antennas by two MW generators (MX4000D, Muegge, 2.45 GHz) working at a pulse frequency of up to 500 Hz, the MW power ON/OFF pulse cycle was set to 6:3 ms. A two-step CVD procedure with nominally “flat” starting diamond growth in the first step (hydrogen-rich gas mixture) and porous diamond growth in the second step (oxygen-rich gas mixture) was employed [25]. The deposition parameters are summarized in Table S1.

Then, the surface of the initial porous diamond film was overgrown with a thin layer (i.e. labeled as an overgrown layer) of Si-doped diamond in a focused microwave plasma system [33], clean (non-seeded) Si wafer pieces placed near the substrates were used as a solid source of silicon and the deposition process parameters are summarized in Table S2.

TD approach

In the TD approach, firstly, the ultra-nanocrystalline diamond (UNCD) films with a thickness of 5.5 μm were grown on Si substrates in the focused microwave plasma system (P6, Aixtron). During the CVD growth, clean (non-seeded) Si wafer pieces placed near the substrates were used as a solid source of silicon. The deposition process parameters for the growth of UNCD films with SiV centers are summarized in Table S3.

To turn the continuous UNCD films into porous ones, they were treated with a molten salt thermal etching (MSTE) process [30]. First, an aqueous solution of 1.0 M LiNO₃ (99.5%, Carl Roth) was prepared by dissolving 1.767 g of pure substance in 25 ml of laboratory-grade DI water. Then, 20 μL of the 1M of LiNO₃ solution was deposited on the UNCD samples by drop-casting technique. The samples covered with LiNO₃ were treated at 450 °C for 5 hours under ambient atmosphere in a laboratory furnace. Then, the formed porous UNCD films were cleaned in a solution of 1.0 M HCl (35%, Penta Chemicals) in an ultrasonic bath (Transonic T 490 DH, Elma, 40 kHz) for 5 min, followed by DI water rinse and dried by nitrogen.

Surface termination of porous diamond films

To investigate the effect of surface termination on photoluminescence (PL) emission of SiV color centers, the BU and TD porous diamond films were treated in either hydrogen or oxygen plasma. As the starting point, the BU and TD porous diamond samples were first treated by the hydrogen plasma in the focused microwave plasma to achieve the hydrogen-terminated surface for both porous films, Table S4. The oxygen surface termination of the BU and TD porous diamond samples was done using radiofrequency oxygen plasma (Diener Electronic – FEMTO, 13.56 MHz), Table S5.

Fabrication of nanodiamonds

The DI water-based SiV-containing nanodiamonds (SiV NDs) colloids were prepared from BU or TD porous diamond samples. In the case of BU samples, the diamond film was first mechanically peeled off from the substrate. Then, the peeled-off material was dispersed in 2 ml DI water and treated in an ultrasonic bath (Transonic T 490 DH, Elma, 40 kHz) for 10 min. In the case of TD samples, the SiV NDs colloid was prepared by dispersing of porous film in 1 ml DI water and treated by an ultrasonic horn (Hielscher UP200S, 24 kHz) at the power of 200 W lasting for 1h.

Material characterization

The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of BU and TD porous diamond films were acquired at 10 kV under 0° (top-view) and 90° (cross-section view) in the regime of secondary electrons (e-Line system, Raith GmbH, Germany).

The Raman and PL measurements were acquired using an InVia Reflex Raman microscope (Renishaw) equipped with the laser with an excitation wavelength of 442 nm (Dual Wavelength HeCd, model IK5651R-G, Kimmon Koha) and air-cooled CCD camera. The samples were excited by a continuous wave laser (the power of 2.6 mW) focused to a spot of 1 μm on the sample in a perpendicular direction to the sample plane using 100 \times objective Leica with NA=0.9. Raman spectra of BU and TD porous diamond samples were accumulated for 30 seconds, and the spectra were sampled 5 times. PL spectra were accumulated for 10 seconds and sampled 3 times. To quantify the portion of diamond to non-diamond carbon phases, the baseline inferred by asymmetric least square smoothing method (ALS, asymmetric factor 5E-5, threshold 0.005, smoothing factor of 4, and 20 iterations) was subtracted from Raman spectra. After that, all spectra were normalized to the intensity of the diamond peak and fitted by Lorenz and Gaussian curves. The PL emission spectra were corrected for the spectral dependence of the apparatus response. To eliminate the effect of PL background on SiV center PL, the PL background was plotted with the B-spline interpolation method (10 anchor points found with the 1st and 2nd derivation method) and subtracted from the total spectrum. After that, the integral intensity of the SiV zero-phonon line maximum around 13 540 cm^{-1} (738.55 nm) as an integrated area under the curve was determined. In the case of SiV NDs made from BU and TD porous diamond samples, the prepared colloids were drop cast on a flat Si substrate, dried, and analyzed using the aforementioned Raman and PL measurement setup.

Temperature-resolved spectroscopy was performed using a custom built temperature-controlled sample stage. The sample was excited by a 532 nm (Thorlabs CPS 532) and 638 (PicoQuant, PDL 800-D, LDH-D-C-640B) laser sources to excite SiV color centers and also check the possible presence of other defects (like nitrogen-vacancy (NV) center) incorporated during the CVD growth process. The emission from the sample was collected via a long working distance microscope objective (Zeiss LD C Epiplan-APOCHROMAT 50x, 0.6 NA).

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) and zeta-potential (ζ) measurements of SiV NDs were performed on a Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS equipped with a helium-neon laser (633 nm), and the scattering angle was 173°. The refractive index of bulk diamond (2.4) and the viscosity of pure water (1.020 mPa·s) were used to convert the measured intensity/size distributions to volume/size distributions.

The size and shape of SiV ND particles were analyzed by a transmission electron microscope (TEM) FEI Tecnai G2 20 with LaB6 cathode at an acceleration voltage of 200 kV. The transmission electron microscope was equipped with a CCD camera Olympus Veleta.

Results and discussions

Surface morphology of BU and TD porous diamond films

Representative top and cross-sectional SEM images of porous diamond films (BU approach) are shown in Figure 1. The initial porous diamond film consists of randomly distributed dendrite-like diamond nanograins with a thickness ranging from 10 to 30 nm and lengths varying between 50 and 200 nm (Fig. 1a, 1b). The maximum distance between these nanograins does not exceed 100 nm, indicating the maximum size of the created nanopores. The total thickness of the diamond film is approximately 340 nm. Such unconventional growth of dendrite-like diamonds has previously been reported only for a pulsed microwave plasma system with a linear antenna arrangement using a low working gas pressure in combination with a high CO₂ content in the gas mixture [25,32].

Figure 1: Surface morphology of the BU sample - top and cross-sectional SEM images of the initial porous diamond film without SiV centers (a, b) and the porous diamond film overgrown with a thin diamond film containing SiV centers (c, d).

In the BU approach, the starting layer was formed during the first growth step, known as the “hydrogen-rich” growth regime (Table S1). This layer exhibits a flat and compact morphology, reaching a thickness of approximately 50 nm before the second growth regime is turned on. The second growth regime is characterized by a high CO₂ content, resulting in a high amount of oxygen species (-O, -OH). These species preferentially attack less stable defects in the diamond crystals, enhancing the surface re-nucleation process and ultimately leading to the formation of porous morphology. The strong etching effect is evident in the cross-sectional SEM image (Fig. 1b), where the lighter bottom area indicates partial etching of the *primary layer* during the early formation of the *porous layer*. However, the high CO₂ content in the gas mixture suppresses the formation of optically active SiV centers, as demonstrated in our earlier studies [8,33]. Consequently, subsequent overgrowth of the porous diamond film with a Si-doped diamond layer is necessary to incorporate the SiV centers.

Figures 1c and 1d show SEM images of the initially porous diamond film overgrown with a thin diamond film containing SiV centers. The final diamond film still remains highly porous, with only a slight smoothing of fine dendritic morphology. Thus, the BU approach results in a core-shell-like porous structure, where the core consists of intrinsic diamond and the shell comprises the SiV-containing diamond film, as later confirmed by PL measurements. Importantly, the final dendrite-like porous diamond structure is brittle, making it suitable for mechanical disintegration into individual NDs.

Representative top and cross-sectional SEM images of the initial and MSTE-treated UNCD diamond films (TD approach) are depicted in Figure 2. The surface morphology of the initial SiV-containing diamond film (Fig. 2a) reveals nano-sized diamond crystals, predominantly ranging from 20 to 50 nm, which are homogeneously distributed throughout the entire thickness (Fig. 2b).

Figure 2: Surface morphology of the TD sample - top and cross-sectional SEM images of the initial UNCD film (a, b), and MSTE-treated UNCD film (c, d).

The initial thickness of UNCD film is approximately 5.5 μm . After the MSTE treatment, which involves annealing in air at 450 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 hours with LiNO_3 (Fig. 2c and 2d), the film exhibits a nanoporous character with a slightly reduced thickness to approximately 5.4 μm . During the MSTE processes, non-diamond sp^1 hybridized (*trans*-polyacetylene) and sp^2 hybridized carbon phases (amorphous carbon, graphitic carbon) are preferentially etched away due to higher reactivity with oxygen species (NO_2 , O_2) compared to sp^3 hybridized diamond [34]. Since these are predominantly localized at the grain boundaries, a porous diamond matrix is formed throughout the entire film thickness (Fig. 2d).

The presence of the molten LiNO_3 salt on the diamond surface affects the chemical reactions and eliminates the amount of sp^1 and sp^2 bonded carbon phases by a set of the following set of reactions [35,36]:

This series of chemical reactions leads to uniform selective etching of sp^1 and sp^2 hybridized carbons at 450 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The resulting porous diamond film is sufficiently brittle, with weakened inter-crystalline bonds, allowing it to be easily transformed into the sub-100 nm fragments of NDs. Since the SiV centers are already embedded in the diamond crystals, the TD approach does not require any additional overgrowth, unlike the BU approach.

Raman spectroscopy and photoluminescence of BU and TD porous diamond films

To evaluate the material quality of the prepared diamond films and the photoluminescence (PL) properties of SiV centers, Raman spectroscopy and PL measurements were conducted.

Figure 3a displays the Raman spectra of the initial porous and Si-doped overgrown porous diamond films (BU approach). The spectrum of the initial porous film (blue) shows only a single sharp peak centered at 1330 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the zone center mode of the sp^3 carbon phase. This confirms excellent diamond phase purity specific to the CO_2 -rich growth regime [32]. In contrast, the Raman spectrum of the overgrown Si-doped diamond film (red) reveals additional bands, although it is still

dominated by a narrow and intense peak related to the diamond phase. Broad bands centered at approximately 1356 cm^{-1} (D band) and 1552 cm^{-1} (G-band) are associated with sp^2 carbon phases. Two other broad bands centered at 1153 cm^{-1} and 1473 cm^{-1} correspond to the carbon-hydrogen bending and carbon-carbon stretching modes of *trans*-polyacetylene (*t*-PA) located at the grain boundaries [37,38]. The former can be considered direct evidence of nanometer-sized diamond grains.

The higher quality of the primary porous diamond layer compared to the overgrown layer is attributed to the high oxygen content in the gas mixture, which effectively etches away the non-diamond carbon phases during the CVD growth. Consequently, the film is almost purely composed of sp^3 phases, where surface defects act as the new nucleation centers, preventing the formation of large diamond crystals, and finally the crystal growth and resulting in a porous dendrite-like morphology.

The top diamond layer containing SiV centers must be grown without oxygen content in the gas mixture, as oxygen suppresses the formation of optically active SiV centers [33,39]. This inevitably leads to the formation of sp^2 phases and CH_x species on the diamond surface, such as *trans*-polyacetylene chains (*t*-PA), as confirmed by the Raman spectroscopy (Fig. 3a, red line). Given that the scattering cross-section of sp^2 bonds in the Raman spectrum excited by visible light is 50 times larger [38], the overgrown film can be still considered as a nanocrystalline film with a distinct diamond character.

Figure 3: a) Raman spectra of the BU initial porous diamond film without SiV centers (blue) and the overgrown porous diamond film with SiV centers (red). b) Raman spectra of the TD initial UNCD film (blue) and the MSTE-treated diamond film (red) (532 nm line excitation laser).

Raman spectra of the TD sample before and after the MSTE treatment are shown in Fig. 3b. The spectrum of the initial diamond film (blue) reveals relatively intense non-diamond carbon features, dominated by *t*-PA bands (1149 cm^{-1} and 1508 cm^{-1}) and the D and G bands (1352 cm^{-1} and 1572 cm^{-1}). A weak diamond peak is also resolved at 1331.5 cm^{-1} .

After MSTE treatment (red), a significant reduction of non-diamond phases is observed, and the sharp diamond peak (1331.5 cm^{-1}) becomes well-recognizable. The *t*-PA bands have completely disappeared, and the intensity of the D and G bands has significantly decreased, indicating selective removal of the non-diamond phases located at the grain boundaries. The G band now consists of two main bands: a peak around 1560 cm^{-1} attributed to the usual G_1 mode of graphite due to the in-plane bond stretching motion of pairs of sp^2 carbon atoms [40], and a downshifted G_2 band at 1534 cm^{-1} attributed to amorphous carbon [41].

Photoluminescence spectra of BU and TD diamond films are shown in Figure 4. For the BU porous diamond layer grown at a high oxygen content, no PL signal was detected at the position of the SiV zero phonon line (ZPL) at 738.8 nm (Fig. 4a, blue curve). This indicates that the primary BU porous sample

is free of optically active SiV centers in the diamond layer as the result of the specific growth conditions discussed above [33,39]. In contrast, the porous diamond layer overgrown in the focused MW plasma system reveals a strong SiV ZPL at 738.8 nm with a typical red-shifted sideband [15,42]. This can be explained by the core-shell structure, where non-photoluminescent diamond grains (core) are coated with a thin SiV-active diamond layer (shell).

We further investigated to which extent the SiV PL emission can be controlled by hydrogen or oxygen surface termination of a porous diamond layer using plasma treatment. As illustrated in Figs. 4b and 4c, both hydrogenated and oxidized BU and TD samples exhibit enhanced SiV signals compared to the as-grown sample. Although hydrogenation does not completely suppress SiV photoluminescence, oxygen surface termination results in a threefold increase in SiV PL intensity relative to the H-terminated sample.

These findings are well consistent with previous studies. Yang, et al. reported a 1470-fold increase in PL intensity for SiV centers in diamond samples annealed in air at 700 °C for 20 min [34]. This enhancement was attributed to a shift from non-radiative recombination (quenching for H-termination or sp² carbon absorption) to radiative processes (O-termination, lower sp² content). Such surface termination-induced PL enhancement requires optical centers to be predominantly located in close proximity to the diamond surface. Our earlier study [43] demonstrated complete on/off switching of SiV photoluminescence by O-/H-termination for diamond films thinner than 10 nm. The incomplete switching observed in the present BU sample suggests that the top overgrown diamond layer containing optically active SiV centers exceeds 10 nm in thickness.

In contrast to the BU porous diamond overgrown with SiV-containing diamond film, surface O-/H-termination has a weaker effect on TD diamond films. This may be due to a more uniform distribution of SiV centers throughout the diamond crystal volume or additional factors such as different growth regimes of diamond nanocrystals during the re-nucleation or variations in light absorptions between the BU and TD porous, etc. Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that despite the different BU and TD approaches, the PL emission behavior exhibits a similar surface-termination sensitivity trend.

SEM, Raman, and PL measurements indicate that the BU approach is more suitable for fabricating SiV-containing porous diamond layers, as overgrown porous crystals demonstrate superior quality/purity and provide a more favorable platform for the effective incorporation of optically active SiV centers. Furthermore, the morphology suppresses competitive non-radiative energy transfer across grain boundaries. These differences are reflected in the SiV ZPL peak parameters (maximum position and FWHM) between the BU and TD samples (see Table 1). We conclude that variations in the size of the optically active regions of diamond crystals and the magnitude of induced stress in the diamond film contribute to these differences [44].

Figure 4: (a) Photoluminescence spectra of BU initial porous diamond film without SiV centers (blue) and the overgrown porous diamond film with SiV centers (red) and (b) overgrown porous diamond films with SiV centers after hydrogenation and oxidization of the diamond surface. Photoluminescence spectra of TD initial and MSTE-treated UNCD films after hydrogenation and oxidization of the diamond surface (c). Comparison of SiV integral intensities for porous diamond films prepared by BU (left) and TD (right) approaches (d) (532 nm line excitation laser).

Table 1: SiV ZPL data for BU and TD porous structures terminated by H₂ and O₂ plasma. Data for fabricated BU/TD NDs are also added.

Approach	Termination	FWHM (cm ⁻¹)	SiV ZPL (nm)
BU	H ₂ plasma	115	738.8
	O ₂ plasma	112	739.0
	Nanodiamonds*	135	738.7
TD	H ₂ plasma	134	739.6
	O ₂ plasma	158	739.5
	Nanodiamonds*	237	739.8

* nanodiamonds produced from O-terminated porous films

Size, structure, and yield of PL-emitting nanodiamonds

In the subsequent technological stage, we disintegrated the oxidized porous BU and TD samples into individual NDs. Sonication was employed as a common method to disperse NDs in liquids and disaggregate them due to weakened intercrystallite bonds [45,46]. The volumetric size distributions of the fabricated NDs from the BU and TD samples, as determined by DLS, are plotted in Figures 5a and 5b, respectively. For the BU sample, the size distribution ranges from 60 nm to 500 nm (indicated by

the green lines), with the dominant fraction between 120 nm to 300 nm (yellow rectangle) and a maximum intensity at 220 nm (brown line).

TEM analysis (Fig. 5c) reveals a representative ND cluster with an elongated dendrite-like shape, comprising smaller NDs (50 nm) and larger NDs with a total length of 230 nm. These observations corroborate the SEM images of the SiV-overgrown BU porous diamond layer shown in Fig. 1, suggesting that the ND cluster resulted from the disintegration of the porous precursor layer. The average zeta-potential (ζ) for SiV-NDs produced by the BU process is -24.6 mV, and the indicative value of oxidized NDs.

For the TD sample, the volumetric size distribution extends from 40 nm to 500 nm with the dominant fraction between 75 nm and 280 nm (yellow rectangle) and a maximum intensity at 220 nm (brown line). The volume distribution around 100 nm is notably higher for the TD sample compared to the BU sample.

TEM analysis (Fig. 5d) shows a representative 200×100 nm cluster composed of 10-40 nm individual NDs. Smaller fragments and individual NDs (indicated by yellow arrows in Fig. 5d) were also identified. The zeta-potential of SiV-NDs produced by the TD approach is -32.9 mV, resulting from their oxidized surface after MSTE and plasma treatment [47].

Figure 5: DLS size volume distribution (a, b), corresponding representative TEM images (c, d), and schematic visualization of individual SiV NDs in a cluster (e, f) of SiV NDs produced by BU (a, c and e) and TD (b, d, and f) approaches.

The successful fabrication of SiV light-emitting colloiddally stable NDs using both BU and TD approaches is demonstrated in Fig. 6. PL spectra exhibit dominant SiV ZPL maxima for both NDs types, with line shapes comparable to those of the porous diamond films (see Figure 4), confirming that the disaggregation treatment did not adversely affect the SiV PL parameters. Notably, BU-produced NDs display ZPL position at lower values by approximately 0.6 nm (Table 1), which can be attributed to the different morphology (core-shell) and released strain of the overgrown SiV NDs [48]. TD SiV NDs also exhibit larger FWHM values, potentially due to the more defective character of constituting diamond nanocrystals (crystallographic defects and nitrogen-related stress resulting from high nitrogen content in the gas mixture).

These observations provide direct proof-of-concept for the successful fabrication of optically active SiV NDs employing both BU and TD approaches. A key technological advance of both methods is their technological simplicity eliminating the need for additional steps commonly required in other techniques (i.e. neutron irradiation, ion implantation, annealing, etc.) [14,49].

Figure 6: a) Normalized PL spectra of SiV NDs fabricated using BU and TD approaches (532 nm line excitation laser). Inset – photograph of TD SiV NDs dispersed in deionized water. b) Normalized PL spectra of SiV NDs fabricated using TD measured at 30 °C (blue) and 90 °C (black) (638 nm excitation laser).

The sensitivity of color centers in diamonds to temperature changes makes them suitable for temperature measurement. Our samples are particularly interesting in this aspect as they provide the platform for nanothermometry, e.g. in living cells [50]. To demonstrate this functionality, we performed spectral measurements (including time-resolved) for a wide range of temperatures (from 30 to 100 °C) using a 638 nm excitation laser. The ZPL position shows a red shift and spectral broadening as the temperature increases, see Fig. 6b for 30 °C and 90 °C. This behavior is mainly attributed to the thermal lattice expansion that reduces the orbital overlap in bonds [51]. An excitation wavelength of 638 nm is preferred due to the reduction of the background signal associated with NV and other color centers. Under excitation with a 532 nm laser line, NDs indeed demonstrate the presence of NV⁰ color centers due to the nitrogen background in the CVD mixture as mentioned above (Fig. S1).

The ZPL shows a linear spectral red shift with a 0.022 ± 0.003 nm/K sensitivity, as shown in Fig 7a, while the linewidth exhibits spectral broadening of 0.068 ± 0.004 nm/K (Fig. 7b). Previous works have mainly reported spectral changes in a smaller temperature ranges. For instance, spectral red shift of 0.011 ± 0.002 nm/K and halfwidth broadening of 0.011 ± 0.002 nm/K was reported using detonation nanodiamonds (for the temperature range of 22 °C – 40.5 °C) [52] and 0.011 ± 0.013 nm/K spectral shift for HPHT fabricated nanodiamonds (for the temperature range of 25 °C – 37.5 °C) [50]. Recent reports on bulk diamonds show a spectral shift of 0.0124 ± 0.0002 nm/K (for a temperature range of 15 °C – 29 °C) [53] and 0.016 ± 0.003 nm/K (for a temperature range of 20 °C – 90 °C) [54]. Time resolved measurements using time-correlated-single-photon-counter show that the excited-state lifetime remains the same in the measured temperature ranges (20 °C - 90 °C), see supplementary material Fig. S2.

Figure 7: Temperature dependence of ZPL position (a) and of FWHM for SiV NDs fabricated by TD approach (638 nm excitation laser).

Finally, an important parameter in the fabrication of SiV NDs is the obtainable amount, i.e. production yield. For instance, the HPHT fabrication of NDs containing NV centers yields an estimated 10% [55,56]. The effective production of SiV NDs has been intensively studied using both HPHT and CVD techniques. The HPHT process (BU approach, direct ND synthesis from organic precursors) has demonstrated reliability in producing tens of mg of NDs in size to 10 nm with high crystallographic quality and bright SiV photoluminescence [17,56,57]. There are still many technological challenges preventing the process from becoming more widespread.

Microwave plasma CVD processes relying on the self-doping of NDs from the silicon substrate are commonly used as one of the simplest methods. Li et al. reported narrow PL linewidth and high optical stability of SiV-grown NDs [58]. Recently Bogdanov et al. introduced a dual-doping process for fabricating SiV and GeV doped NDs [59]. However, such a CVD fabrication typically yields only a few > 100 nm NDs per run. Further CVD technological progress applying a multi-layer-like compartment was presented by Dallaire et al. [21]. This process was subsequently optimized by Feudis et al., who achieved a production yield of a few mg NDs per CVD run [22]. In contrast to the BU approaches (i.e. HPHT and CVD processes), ball milling has been applied as the TD approach. However, only a proof-of-concept level has been achieved due to limitations such as the large consumption of cleaning chemicals (mainly acids) and the long-term treatment needed for ND purification [20].

In this work, we applied a multilayer-like compartment strategy similar to that of Dallaire et al. [21], yet unique technological steps were developed for the fabrication of SiV porous diamond layers using either the BU or TD approach. Our approaches can yield 22 mg for BU (1 μm thick diamond on 4 inches with 20% weight losses) and 28 mg for TD (6 μm thick film on 2 inches with 30% weight losses) in one run, considering 100% conversion of the NCD film to NDs.

Due to the sharp and narrow line of SiV PL, the BU core-shell approach is promising for fabricating high-quality surface-fluorescent NDs. However, technological improvements are still needed to directly grow doped porous films using the linear antenna CVD technique.

For the TD approach, hundreds of milligrams of ND can be easily produced due to the simplicity of UNCD growth and the applicability of the MSTE process to thick films (>50 μm). As an extension of this concept, we also successfully produced porous boron-doped NCD film [30] and boron-doped NDs using the TD approach. Thus, the presented technological approaches are generally applicable and can be used to produce differently doped NDs.

Conclusion

In this study, we demonstrated successful fabrication of nanodiamonds containing optically active silicon-vacancy (SiV) color centers using two innovative approaches: bottom-up and top-down, both based on CVD processes. These methods provided highly nano-porous diamond films with bright SiV photoluminescence, suitable for mechanical disintegration into SiV NDs.

The BU approach included the CVD growth of a high-quality, low $\text{sp}^2\text{-C}$, dendrite-like, porous diamond structure followed by the growth of a thin SiV diamond film, preserving the initial porous morphology and yielding superior diamond quality. The TD approach included growth of a 5.5 μm thick, continuous, fine-grained ultrananocrystalline diamond film directly doped with SiV centers throughout, followed by molten-salt thermal etching. This ensured the selective removal of non-diamond carbon from the grain boundaries, resulting in a uniform, nano-porous structure.

Raman spectroscopy and photoluminescence measurements confirmed high-quality diamond phases and successful, near-surface SiV incorporation in both approaches. Notably, both SiV-containing nanoporous diamond films exhibited sensitivity to oxygen and hydrogen surface terminations, with higher SiV zero-phonon line emission observed for oxidized surfaces, particularly in BU samples.

SiV NDs were obtained by ultrasonic disintegration of both types of nanoporous SiV diamond films. Dynamic light scattering and transmission electron microscopy analyses revealed that BU-produced NDs ranged from 60-500 nm with elongated dendrite-like shapes, while TD-produced NDs ranged from 40-500 nm, containing smaller individual 5-50 nm nanocrystals. Both approaches yielded colloiddally stable solutions and comparable size distributions.

Importantly, the strong SiV photoluminescence intensity of individual NDs remained consistent with that of the porous diamond films, without requiring time-consuming post-treatment to remove non-diamond phases. This represents a significant advancement over previously published works, introducing a more efficient production process. The SiV NDs exhibited stable emission at high temperatures which allows the platform to be used as a temperature sensor above biological temperature range. The linear spectral response of the color centers with temperature and the nanoscale dimensions are promising for future nanothermometry applications.

The developed techniques provide promising routes for further development of functional nanoscale diamond structures, offering potential applications in quantum sensing, bioimaging, thermometry, biological labeling, optoelectrical hybrid heterostructures, and other quantum technologies. This work paves the way for cost-effective, well-controlled, high-yield production of NDs with incorporated optically active (Si, N) or electrically active dopants (B, P), addressing the growing demand for these nanomaterials in various advanced fields.

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